

CLUSTERING AND ITS DEVELOPMENT

¹Alieva J.A., ²Djumaniyazova M.R., ³Khusenova Dildora

¹Senior Lecturer of "SIM" Department

²Senior teacher of English of "Foreign languages" Department

³Student of TICT "Economics and Management of Industry" department

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10848596>

The goal cannot be achieved without deep reforms in the industrial sector.

In the Strategy of actions on five priority directions of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021, which was adopted on the initiative of the President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, in the branches of industry in priority directions defined to improve the competitiveness of the country's economy has acquired great importance.

The term "cluster" is a French word and Uzbek translation means "claw", "head", "bundle", "group", "gathering", "settlement". Also "cluster" is presented as a sampling research method.

The theory of "cluster" is based on Alfred Marshall's opinion on the integration of specialised industries in separate regions in his book "Principles of Economics" (1890), written at the end of the XIX century. Territorial integration of specialised enterprises based on his scientific conclusions:

- Availability of skilled labour resources;
- the growth of suppliers and complementary industries;
- it is based on the existence of specialisation of different firms at different stages of the production process.

The multifaceted nature of the "cluster" theory has led to the formation of different theoretical approaches to it.

After 1980s we can observe the achievements of three important scientific schools (American, British, Scandinavian and others) in the development of "Cluster Theory".

American scientists: M. Porter "Theory of competitive advantage", M. Enright, S. Resenfeld, P. Maskell and M. Laurentsen "Concept of regional clusters", A. Marshall "Theory of industrial regions", P. Bekatin ". Theories of Italian Industrial Districts", M. Storper created theories of the "ideal" regional cluster". This group also includes value added and "the cohesiveness of the cluster chain, regional learning concepts". The theories of these scholars emphasize that clusters are highly effective in increasing the competitive advantage of producers and are a system combined with the activities of educational, scientific, technological, economic and other service actors in the region. .

According to British theorists (D. Dunning, K. Breeman, Schmidt, J. Humphries), cluster is an institutional theory that defines the basis of the economy as a system of institutions of mutual co-operation. At the same time, the "cluster" itself is considered as a "modern institution". They want to say that the interaction of participants in this system is different - formal and informal, and the external scope of clusters is also wide.

Scandinavian scientists (B.O.Lundvall, B.Johnson, B.Asheim, A.Isaacson) - the view that the evolutionary development of a cluster goes through a number of stages, i.e. "from birth to completion" - this indicates that using the possibility of evolutionary theory means that the theory of "cluster" does

Another fourth group of scholars considers the Cluster as a modern paradigm of regional development based on the concepts of "region-corporation dominance", "region-market dominance", "region-state dominance", "territory-social dominance". .

Russian scientists Y.S.Artomonova, B.B.Khurustalyov and others are studying the theory of clusters, and projects for its implementation are being developed. The creation of the above theories and their practical significance suggest that the economies of countries, industries and enterprises will increase their competitiveness and achieve high efficiency.

From the evolution of the "cluster" theory, two of its fundamental characteristics can be identified.

Firstly, the activities of enterprises and firms integrated into a cluster must be related to the market of similar goods. Such dependence is vertical (chain of purchase and sale) and horizontal (use of additional departments and services, special costs, technologies or institutions and other links).

Second, clusters are groups of interdependent enterprises located geographically close, and as a result of stabilization of mutual economic and social relations between them there is a development of competitiveness, creation of opportunities to create more added value and market sales.

Initially, clusters were created only due to the "invisible hand of the market" (competition), primarily in the modernization of multinational companies, and later they are helped by many governments, although they have a significant impact on this process. Due to the attractiveness of the cluster strategy and diversity of directions, the government itself requires the formation of innovation clusters. Cluster initiation is a controlled process of cluster creation and development. Cluster policy is the process by which government and public organizations promote the growth of clusters and cluster initiatives.

It can also be seen as a new economic system that fully meets the requirements of national and regional development.

Developed countries have accumulated certain experience of using clusters in the formation and management of innovation economy. This strategy is widely used in European countries and the USA. Clusters are well developed in the UK, the Netherlands, Germany, the USA, Denmark, France, Italy, Finland, India. The industries of Denmark, Finland and Sweden are saturated with clusters.

Cluster structures are successfully operating in the light industry in Switzerland, Austria, Italy, Denmark, India, Korea, Pakistan, China and Turkey, in the chemical and machine-building industry in Germany, in the food and cosmetics industry in France.

The process of cluster formation is intensifying in South-East Asia, China, Singapore, Japan and other countries.

Until recently, the development of clusters in Germany took place without government intervention. In 2003, the government paid serious attention to cluster initiatives. First of all, this was realized in the design of high-tech industries. The state plans to combine the efforts of industrial and scientific centers.

List of used literature:

1. The new version of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Foreign Economic Activity Tashkent city, May 26, 2000, No. 77-II
2. I.A. Khamedov, A.M. Alimov - "Fundamentals of foreign economic activity in the Republic of Uzbekistan" - T. 2001.
3. Information of the State Statistics Committee;
4. www.mfer.uz
5. <https://review.uz/uz>
6. <https://uz.wikipedia.org>
7. <https://www.gazeta.uz>